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Updated checklist of Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) of Iran, with some new records

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ABSTRACT. An updated checklist of 129 species in 62 genera belonging to 10 subfamilies of Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) known from Iran is presented. One genus, *Trychnosoma* Graham, 1957 and three species, *Systasis ephedrae* Dzhanokmen, 1982; *Trychnosoma punctipleura* Thomson, 1878 and *Spalangia rugulosa* Förster, 1850 are newly recorded for the fauna of Iran. Hosts and distributional data in Iran are also presented.

Key words: Catalogue, distribution, hosts, Iran, new records, Pteromalidae

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Introduction

The Pteromalidae is one of the largest families in the Chalcidoidea superfamily, including over 3,545 species belonging to 588 genera (Noyes, 2016). The pteromalids are primary or secondary parasitoids attacking other insect groups such as Coleoptera, Diptera, Lepidoptera, Hymenoptera, Hemiptera and some Arachnida in their various stages of development (Bouček & Rasplus, 1991; Desjardins, Rejier & Mitter, 2007). A few species of this family are phytophagous (Farooqi & Menon, 1972). Some of them develop in the seeds of plants, others are gall maker and others develop as inquilines in galls caused by other insects (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2016). They play an important role in the control of

insect pests and several species have been employed successfully in biological control programs all over the world (Greathead, 1986; Debach & Rosen, 1991; Bouček & Rasplus, 1991).

The first publication on Pteromalidae of Iran were made by Davachi and Chodjai (1968) who presented the first list of Iranian parasitoids that included only seven pteromalid species. Several species records were initially published by Steffan (1968) and Sharifi and Javadi (1971). After these few initial works, more contributions have been carried out for collecting and identifying the Iranian Pteromalidae in various regions of Iran by several researchers (Goldansaz, Esmaili & Ebadi,

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1996; Lotfalizadeh & Ahmadi, 1998, 2000; Sadeghi & Askary, 2001; Mashhadi-Jafarloo & Talebi-Chaichi, 2002; Sadeghi & Ebrahimi, 2002; Habibpour, Kamali & Meidani, 2002; Jalilvand & Gholipour, 2002; Sadeghi & Ebrahimi, 2002; Mehrnejad, 2002, 2003; Rezaei, Moharrampour & Talebi, 2003; Lotfalizadeh, 2002 a; Lotfalizadeh, 2002 b; Lotfalizadeh, 2004; Hadi, Kazemi & Lotfalizadeh, 2016; Lotfalizadeh, Alehosein & Fallahzadeh, 2017). Lotfalizadeh and Gharali (2008) presented first informative checklist which reported 78 species of Pteromalidae from different parts of Iran including biological and geographical distribution data. They compared the composition of species with those of the world and the Palaearctic region. Recently other records have been added to the pteromalid fauna of Iran (Alemansour, Asadi & Alehosein, 2010; Hesami et al., 2010; Nazemi-Rafie & Lotfalizadeh, 2010; Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011; Hasani, Mitroiu & Madjdzadeh, 2011; Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2013; Mahdavi & Madjdzadeh, 2013; Alipanah, Nazemi-Rafie & Lotfalizadeh, 2013; Lotfalizadeh & Hosseini, 2014; Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2014; Ebrahimi, 2014; Bayegan et al., 2014; Ziaaddini et al., 2014; Hashemi & Lotfalizadeh, 2014; Lotfalizadeh, 2015; Mahdavi, Madjdzadeh & Mitroiu, 2015; Lotfalizadeh, Bayegan & Zargarani, 2016). Universal Chalcidoidea database provided pteromalid species of Iran (Noyes, 2016), but the results of some studies on this family in Iran were not included in the database. The aim of this paper is to present an updated checklist of pteromalid species, their hosts as well as their distribution in Iran.

Material and methods

The updated checklist is provided based on reviewing all literatures on the distribution and host records of Pteromalidae in Iran.

Synonyms, worldwide distributions and extralimital host information for the species are not included because these data are readily accessible in Universal Chalcidoidea Database (Noyes, 2016). Some recently collected specimens were identified by second author and were added to Iranian fauna of Pteromalidae. The species are arranged alphabetically. Seventy-seven pteromalid species were reported in the Universal Chalcidoidea Database, but here 49 other species (marked with an asterisk, *) are added to the previous records. The new genera and species records for Iran are marked with two asterisks (**). The classification and taxonomic arrangement follow Noyes (2016).

The material was collected during 2007-2013 from different parts of Iran, and they are held in the Department of Plant Protection, East-Azarbaijan Research & Education Center for Agriculture & Natural Resources, Tabriz, Iran. The individuals were collected using different methods including Malaise trap, pan trap and sweep net. Identification was made by HL using keys provided by Bouček (1963), Bouček and Rasplus (1991) and Dzhankov (1996).

Results

Checklist of Pteromalidae of Iran Family Pteromalidae Dalman, 1820 Subfamily 1. Asaphinae Ashmead, 1904

Genus: *Asaphes* Walker, 1834

1. *Asaphes suspensus* (Nees, 1834)

Host: This species is hyperparasitoid of *Pemphigus spyrothecae* Passerini, 1860 (Hem.: Aphididae) via *Monoctonia vesicarii* Tremblay, 1991 (Hym.: Braconidae, Aphidiinae) on *Populus nigra* (Ghafouri-Moghaddam, Lotfalizadeh & Rakhshani, 2014).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008), Kerman (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh,

2011; Kordestan (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2013) and Ardabil provinces (Ghafouri-Moghaddam, Lotfalizadeh & Rakhshani, 2014).

2. *Asaphes vulgaris* Walker, 1834*

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (Nazemi Rafie, Alipanah & Lotfalizadeh, 2011).

Subfamily 2. Cerocephalinae Gahan, 1946

Genus: *Theocolax* Westwood, 1832

3. *Theocolax elegans* Westwood, 1874

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Khuzestan (Habibpour, Kamali & Meidani, 2002; Lotfalizadeh and Gharali, 2008), Mazandaran (Lotfalizadeh & Hosseini, 2013) and East-Azərbayjan provinces (Lotfalizadeh & Hosseini, 2013).

4. *Theocolax formiciformis* Westwood, 1832*

Host: Reared on pupae of the rice weevil, *Sitophilus oryzae* Linnaeus, 1763 (Col.: Curculionidae) (Assemi & Shojai, 2004).

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran (Assemi & Shojai, 2004).

Subfamily 3. Cleonyminae Walker, 1837

Genus: *Callocleonymus* Masi, 1940

5. *Callocleonymus pulcher* Masi, 1940*

Host: Reared from *Roguloscolytus mediterraneus* Eggers, 1922 (Col.: Scolytidae) and *Xylopertha reflexicauda* Lesne, 1937 (Col.: Bostrichidae) (Lotfalizadeh & Khalghani, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: East Azarbaijan province (Lotfalizadeh & Khalghani, 2008).

Genus: *Chalcedectus* Walker, 1852

6. *Chalcedectus balachowskyi* Steffan, 1968

Host: It is a parasitoid of larvae of *Osphranteria coerulescens* Redtenbacher, 1850 (Col.: Cerambycidae) on *Rosa* sp.. It was reared on the Rosaceae branch borer (Sharifi & Javadi, 1971).

Distribution in Iran: (no locality cited) (OILB, 1971; Steffan, 1968; Sharifi & Javadi, 1971).

7. *Chalcedectus sinaiticus* (Masi, 1936)

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Hormozagan province (Lotfalizadeh, Alehosein & Fallahzadeh, 2017).

Genus: *Cleonymus* Latreille, 1809

8. *Cleonymus laticornis* Walker, 1837*

Host: *Cleonymus laticornis* is parasitic on xylophagous beetles (Graham, 1969). It was collected from Coleoptera pupa probably belongs to Cerambycidae family on *Prunus divaricata* Ledeb by Damavandian and Feli Kohikheili (2015).

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran province (Damavandian & Feli Kohikheili, 2015).

Genus: *Heydenia* Förster, 1856

9. *Heydenia pretiosa* Förster, 1856

Host: It is a parasitoid of xylophagous beetles (Buprestidae, Scolytidae, Cerambycidae and Curculionidae (Davatchi & Chodjai, 1968; Herting, 1973). It was reared from *Xylopertha reflexicauda* Lesne, 1937 (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008). This specie was also reared from *Ruguloscolytus mediterraneus* Eggers, 1922 and *Phloeosinus bicolor* Brulle, 1832 on fruit trees and *Biota orientalis* L. Endl. (Davatchi & Chodjai, 1968).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azərbayjan (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008) and Alborz provinces (Davatchi & Chodjai, 1968).

Genus: *Oodera* Westwood, 1874

10. *Oodera monstrum* Nikol'skaya, 1952*

Host: It is parasitoid of xylophagous beetles, mainly Buprestidae (Nazemi-Rafie, Alipanah & Lotfalizadeh, 2011; Alipanah, Nazemi-Rafie & Lotfalizadeh, 2013).

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (Nazemi-Rafie, Alipanah & Lotfalizadeh, 2011; Alipanah, Nazemi-Rafie & Lotfalizadeh, 2013).

Genus: *Notanisuus* Walker, 1837

11. *Notanisuus vanharteni* Gibson, 2015

Host: It was reared on *Dorema ammoniacum* (D. Don.) (Apiaceae) (Lotfalizadeh, Alehosein & Fallahzadeh, 2017).

Distribution in Iran: Fars province (Lotfalizadeh, Alehosein & Fallahzadeh, 2017).

Subfamily 4. Colotrechninae Thomson, 1876

Genus: Colotrechnus Thomson, 1878

12. *Colotrechnus viridis* Masi, 1921*

Host: This species was reared on safflower attacked by fruit flies, *Acanthiophilus helianthi* Rossi, 1794, *Chaetorella carthami* Stackelberg, 1929, *Terellia luteola* Wiedemann, 1830 and *Urophora mauritanica* Macquart, 1851 (Dip.: Tephritidae) (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008, 2014).

Distribution in Iran: Ilam (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008, 2014), East-Azarbaijan and Chaharmahal-e-Bakhtiari provinces (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2014).

Subfamily 5. Eunotinae Ashmead, 1904

Genus: Anogmus Förster, 1856

13. *Anogmus laricis* Bouček, 1966*

Host: This species is considered as parasitoid of some Anthomyiidae (Dip.) (Bahri-Motlagh, lotfalizadeh & Mehrvar, 2012).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan province (Bahri-Motlagh, lotfalizadeh & Mehrvar, 2012).

Genus: Eunotus Walker, 1834

14. *Eunotus nigriclavus* Förster, 1856

Host: *Acantholecnium haloxyloni* Hott. (Hem.: Coccidae) (Haeselbarth, 1983).

Distribution in Iran: Northwest of Iran (Haeselbarth, 1983).

Genus: Moranila Cameron, 1883

15. *Moranila californica* (Howard, 1881)

Host: This species is reported as egg predator of *Saissetia oleae* Oliver, 1791, *Ceroplastes floridensis* Comstock, 1881 and *Parthenolecanium* sp. (Davoodi et al., 2004; Jalilvand et al., 2013; Ebrahimi, 2014).

Distribution in Iran: Tehran (Davoodi et al., 2004), Guilan (Ebrahimi, 2014) and Kkermanshah provinces (Jalilvand et al., 2013).

Subfamily 6. Miscogastrinae Walker, 1833

Genus: Halticoptera Spinola, 1811

This genus has been synonymized with *Halticopterina* Erdös, 1946 (Mitroiu, 2014).

16. *Halticoptera aenea* (Walker, 1833)

Host: It is reported as a parasitoid of Agromyzidae in Iran by OILB (1971).

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (OILB, 1971; Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2013).

17. *Halticoptera circulus* (Walker, 1833)

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008) and Kerman provinces (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

18. *Halticoptera longipetiolus* Hedqvist, 1975*

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (Nazemi-Rafie, Alipanah & Lotfalizadeh, 2011).

19. *Halticoptera* cf. *patellana* Dalman, 1818*

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

20. *Halticoptera polita* Walker, 1834*

Host: It is reported as parasitoid of *Phyllonorycter populifoliella* Treitschke, 1833 (Lep.: Gracillariidae) on *Populus* spp. (Sadeghi & Lotfalizadeh, 2012).

Distribution in Iran: West-Azarbaijan province (Sadeghi & Lotfalizadeh, 2012).

21. *Halticoptera violacea* Askew, 1972*

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Hormozgan province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

22. *Halticoptera* cf. *yoncacus* Doğanlar, 2006*

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Khorasan Razavi province (Hasani, Mitroiu & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

23. *Halticoptera moczari* (Erdös, 1954)*

Host: In *Medicago sativa* L. field (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Ksenoplata* Bouček, 1965

24. *Ksenoplata quadrata* Bouček, 1965

Host: It was collected on *Ephedra major* (Hadi, Kazemi & Lotfalizadeh, 2017).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan province (Hadi, Kazemi & Lotfalizadeh, 2017).

Genus: *Miscogaster* Walker, 1833

25. *Miscogaster elegans* Walker, 1833*

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Ilam province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

26. *Miscogaster rufipes* Walker, 1833*

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Ilam province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Subfamily 7. Ormocerinae Walker, 1833

Genus: *Systasis* Walker, 1834

27. *Systasis angustula* Graham, 1969*

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Ardabil province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

28. *Systasis cf. annulipes* (Walker, 1834)*

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

29. *Systasis encyrtoides* Walker 1854

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Kerman (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011), Khorasan Razavi (Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012) and Kordestan provinces (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2013).

30. *Systasis ephedrae* Dzhankmen, 1982**

Material examined: IRAN, Kordestan province, Sanandaj, Darbandeh, 18-V-2013, sweep net, (H. Lotfalizadeh), 4 ♀♀.

Comments: This species known from Georgia and Kazakhstan as parasitoid of gall-midges (Dip.: Cecidomyiidae) (Noyes, 2016). Four species of this genus have been

reported from Iran (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008; Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (new record for Iran).

31. *Systasis longula* Bouček, 1956*

Host: Unknown. This species was swept on *Malus* sp. in Kordestan province (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2016).

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2016).

32. *Systasis parvula* Thomson, 1876*

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Khorasan Razavi province (Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).

33. *Systasis tenuicornis* Walker, 1834*

Host: Unknown. This species was swept on *Malus* sp. in Kordestan province (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2016).

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2016).

Subfamily 8. Pteromalinae Dalman, 1820

Genus: *Anisopteromalus* Ruschka, 1912

34. *Anisopteromalus calandrae* (Howard, 1881)

Host: Reared from *Callosobruchus maculatus* Fabricius, 1775 (Col.: Bruchidae) (Haselbarth 1983; Kazemi et al., 2004; Kazemi, Talebi & Fathipour, 2010; Lotfalizadeh & Hosseini, 2013).

Distribution in Iran: Kermanshah, Qazvin, North-Khorasan, Mazandaran and Sistan-baluchestan provinces (Haselbarth 1983; Kazemi et al., 2004; Kazemi, Talebi & Fathipour, 2010; Lotfalizadeh & Hosseini, 2013).

Genus: *Arthrolytus* Thomson, 1878

35. *Arthrolytus glandium* Bouček, 1967*

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan province (Bahri-Motlagh, lotfalizadeh & Mehrvar, 2012).

36. *Arthrolytus ocellus* (Walker, 1834)*

Host: Reared from galls of *Chilaspis israeli* Sternlicht, 1968 (Hym.: Cynipidae) on *Quercus* sp. (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: Ilam province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Caenacis* Förster, 1856

37. *Caenacis inflexa* Ratzeburg, 1848

Host: Lotfalizadeh, Rasplus & Delvare (2006) reported this species as a parasitoid of rose leaf gall, *Diplolepis* sp. (?*nervosa*) (Hym.: Cynipidae).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan province (Lotfalizadeh, Rasplus & Delvare, 2006; Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Caenocrepis* Thomson, 1878

38. *Caenocrepis bothynoderi* Gromakov, 1940

Host: This species is an egg parasitoid of heliotrope weevil, *Pachycerus cordiger* Germar, 1818 (Col.: Curculionidae) (Huber & Vayssieres, 1990; Mitroiu, 2012).

Distribution in Iran: Qazvin province (Huber & Vayssieres, 1990).

Genus: *Callitula* Spinola, 1811

39. *Callitula bicolor* Spinola, 1811*

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2013).

40. *Callitula ferrierei* Bouček, 1964*

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Guilan province (Bayegan et al., 2014).

Genus: *Catolaccus* Thomson, 1878

41. *Catolaccus ater* (Ratzeburg, 1852)*

Host: This species is a primary and secondary parasitoid of different groups of insects but its hosts in Iran are unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Ilam province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

42. *Catolaccus crassiceps* (Masi, 1911)

Host: This species was reared on cocoon of *Chrysoperla carnea* Stephens, 1836 and *Suaris fedschenkoi* (Mclachlan in Fedchenko, 1875) (Neu.: Chrysopidae) (Lotfalizadeh & Ahmadi, 2000). It was also reared on the cynipid gall wasp, *Diplolepis*

fructuum Rübsaamen, 1882 (Hym.: Cynipidae) (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: Ardabil, East-Azarbaijan, Fars (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008) and Kordestan provinces (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2013).

Genus: *Cecidostiba* Thomson, 1878

43. *Cecidostiba fungosa* (Geoffroy, 1785)*

Host: Reared from *Chilaspis israeli* Sternlicht, 1968 (Hym.: Cynipidae) on *Quercus brantii* Lindl. (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: Lorestan province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Cheiopachus* Westwood, 1829

44. *Cheiopachus quadrum* Fabricius, 1787

Host: Parasitoid of the larvae of *Rogulascolytus mediteraneus* Eggers, 1922 (Col.: Scolytidae) and *Xylopertha reflexicauda* Lesne, 1937 (Col.: Bostrychidae) on dead wood of apple tree (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008), and Kerman provinces (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

Genus: *Chlorocytus* Graham, 1956

45. *Chlorocytus spicatus* (Walker, 1835)*

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Ilam province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Conomorium* Masi, 1924

46. *Conomorium ampulum* Walker, 1835

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (Nazemi Rafie, Alipanah & lotfalizadeh, 2011; Alipanah, Nazemi-Rafie & Lotfalizadeh, 2013).

47. *Conomorium patulum* (Walker, 1835)

Host: This species reared as a gregarious pupal parasitoid of brown tail moth, *Euproctis chrysorrhoea* Linnaeus, 1758 (Nikdel et al., 2007).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarabaijan province (Nikdel et al., 2007).

Genus: *Cyrtogaster* Walker, 1833**48. *Cyrtogaster vulgaris* Walker, 1833**

Host: Reared from crucifer leaf miners, *Chromatomyia horticola* Goureau, 1851 and *Liriomyza sativae* Blanchard, 1938 (Dip.: Agromyzidae) (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan, Ardabil (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008) and Kordestan provinces (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

Genus: *Cyrtoptyx* Delucchi, 1956**49. *Cyrtoptyx cf. latipes* Rondani, 1874**

Host: It was reared from seeds of *Pistacia atlantica* Desf. (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

Distribution in Iran: Kerman (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011) and Khorasan Razavi provinces (Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).

50. *Cyrtoptyx lichtensteini* (Masi, 1921)*

Host: This species has been reported on *Etiella zinckenella* Treitschke, 1832 (Lotfalizadeh & Hosseini, 2014).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan (Lotfalizadeh & Hosseini, 2014).

51. *Cyrtoptyx pistaciae* Nikol'skaya, 1935

Host: It was collected on *Pistacia khinjuk* L. (Jalilvand & Gholipour, 2002).

Distribution in Iran: Qazvin and Lorestan provinces (Jalilvand & Gholipour, 2002; Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Dibrachoides* Kurdjumov, 1913**52. *Dibrachoides dynastes* Förster, 1841**

Host: *Hypera postica* Gyllenhal, 1813 (Col.: Curculionidae) (Lotfalazadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008; Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2013).

Genus: *Dibrachys* Förster, 1856**53. *Dibrachys affinis* Masi, 1907***

Host: This species was reported as a pupae parasitoid of grape berry moth, *Lobesia botrana* Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775 (Lep.:

Tortricidae) (Lotfalizadeh, Masnadi-Yazdinejad & Saber, 2012a).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan province (Lotfalizadeh, Masnadi-Yazdinejad & Saber, 2012a).

54. *Dibrachys microgastris* Bouché, 1834

Host: *Leucoma wiltshirei* Collenette, 1938 (Lep.: Lymanteriidae) and *Kermania pistaciella* Amsel, 1964 (Jafari & Shaigan, 1993). Goldansaz, Esmaili and Ebadi (1996) considered this species as a parasitoid of lesser wax moth, *Achroia grisella* Fabricius, 1794. Mehrnejad (2002, 2003) studied its biological and ecological attributes as a parasitoid of the pistachio twig borer moth, *K. pistaciella* Amsel, 1964 (Lep.: Tineidae). Mashhadi-Jafarloo & Talebi-Chaichi (2002) considered this species as gregarious ectoparasitoid of codling moth (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan (Mashhadi-Jafarloo & Talebi-Chaichi, 2002), Fars (Haeselbarth 1983), Kerman (Jafari & Shaigan, 1993; Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011) and Khorasan Razavi provinces (Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).

55. *Dibrachys lignicola* Graham, 1969*

Host: It was collected from *Salix carmanica* Bornm (Salicaceae) in Rayen, Kerman province by Ziaaddini *et al.* (2014).

Distribution in Iran: Kerman province, Rayen (Ziaaddini *et al.*, 2014).

Genus: *Dinarmus* Thomson, 1878**56. *Dinarmus acutus* (Thomson, 1878)**

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Kerman province (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

57. *Dinarmus basalis* (Rondani, 1877)

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Khorasan Razavi province (Hasani, Mitroiu & Madjdzadeh, 2011; Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).

58. *Dinarmus vagabundus* (Timberlake, 1926)*

Host: This species is a parasitoid of three brachids in Iran (Eslami, 1998)

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan, Mazandaran and Qazvin provinces (Lotfalizadeh & Hosseini, 2013).

Genus: *Dinotiscus* Ghesquière, 1946

59. *Dinotiscus colon* (Linnaeus, 1758)*

Host: Parasitoid of *Ruguloscolytus mediterraneus* Eggers, 1922 and *Phloeosinus bicolor* Brulle, 1832 (Col.: Scolytidae) (Davatchi & Chodjai, 1968, Shojai, 1998 as *Cheiopachus colon* Linnaeus, 1758).

Distribution in Iran: Alborz (Shojai, 1998 as *Cheiopachus colon* L.), Ardabil (Davatchi & Chodjai, 1968; Radjabi, 1991; Shojai, 1998 as *C. colon*; Lotfalizadeh & Khalghani, 2008), Kermanshah, Kordestan (Davatchi & Chodjai, 1968 as *C. colon*; Radjabi, 1991; Lotfalizadeh & Khalghani, 2008), East Azarbaijan, Fars, Hamadan, Isfahan, Lorestan, Markazi, Tehran, Zanjan provinces (Davatchi & Chodjai, 1968; Radjabi, 1991; Lotfalizadeh & Khalghani, 2008).

Genus: *Erdoesina* Graham, 1957

60. *Erdoesina alboannulata* (Ratzeburg, 1852)*

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Euneura* Walker, 1844

61. *Euneura lachni* (Ashmead, 1887)

Host: Hyperparasitoid of Aphididae (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: Iran (OILB, 1971).

Genus: *Gugolzia* Delucchi & Steffan, 1956

62. *Gugolzia bademia* Doğanlar, 2004*

Host: *Eurytoma amygdali* Enderlein, 1907 (Hym.: Eurytomidae) (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: Chaharmahal-e Bakhtiari province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

63. *Gugolzia harmolitae* Delucchi & Steffan, 1956*

Host: *Tetramesa romana* Walker, 1873 (Hym.: Eurytomidae) (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: Ardabil province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Hobbya* Delucchi, 1957

64. *Hobbya stenonota* Ratzeburg, 1848

Host: *Diplolepis fructuum* (Rübsaamen) (Hym.: Cynipidae) (Lotfalizadeh, Rajabi & Madjdzadeh, 2012b).

Distribution in Iran: Kerman province (Lotfalizadeh, Rajabi & Madjdzadeh, 2012b).

Genus: *Homoporus* Thomson, 1878

65. *Homoporus fulviventris* Walker 1835

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Kerman province (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

66. *Homoporus semiluteus* (Walker, 1872)

Host: Its host is unknown but the majority of the Western Palaearctic species of *Homoporus* Thomson are associated with insects that develop in grass stems (Bouček & Rasplus, 1991).

Distribution in Iran: Khorasan Razavi province (Hasani, Mitroiu & Madjdzadeh, 2011; Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).

67. *Homoporus subniger* (Walker, 1835)

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan province (Lotfalizadeh, 2015).

Genus: *Mesopolobus* Westwood, 1833

68. *Mesopolobus amaenus* (Walker, 1834)

Host: *Leucoma wiltshirei* Collenette, 1938 (Lep.: Lymantriidae) (Haeselbarth, 1983) and rose gall wasp, *Diplolepis mayri* Schlechtendal, 1877 (Hym.: Cynipidae) (Askew, Sadeghi & Tavakoli, 2006).

Distribution in Iran: Fars province (Haeselbarth, 1983).

69. *Mesopolobus arcanus* Askew, 1997*

Host: Parasitoid of *Eurytoma* sp. (Hym.: Eurytomidae) on *Epheda procera* Fisch and Mey (Ephedraceae) (Alemansour, Asadi & Alehosein, 2010).

Distribution in Iran: Fars province (Alemansour, Asadi & Alehosein, 2010).

70. *Mesopolobus deserti* Dzhankov, 1994

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Khorasan Razavi province (Hasani, Mitroiu & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

71. *Mesopolobus fasciiventris* Westwood, 1833*

Host: Reared from leaf galls on *Salix pycnostachya* Andersson (Mahdavi & Madjdzadeh, 2013).

Distribution in Iran: Kerman province (Mahdavi & Madjdzadeh, 2013).

72. *Mesopolobus sericeus* (Förster, 1770)*

Host: Collected on *Tamarix* sp. (Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).

Distribution in Iran: Khorasan Razavi province (Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).

73. *Mesopolobus xanthocerus* (Thomson, 1878)*

Host: Collected on Gramineae (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2016).

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2016).

Genus: *Metastenus* Walker, 1834

74. *Metastenus concinnus* Walker, 1834

Host: *Cryptolaemus montrouzieri* Mulsant, 1853 (Col.: Coccinellidae) (Gharizadeh & Hesami, 2003).

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran province (Gharizadeh & Hesami, 2003).

Genus: *Mokrzeckia* Mokrzecki, 1934

75. *Mokrzeckia obscura* Graham, 1969

Host: It is a hyperparasitoid of the diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* (L.) (Lep.: Plutellidae) and act as parasitoid of *Cotesia vestalis* (Haliday, 1834) (Afiunizadeh, Karimzadeh & Lotfalizadeh, 2013; Afiunizadeh & Karimzadeh, 2015).

Distribution in Iran: Isfahan province (Karimzadeh & Lotfalizadeh, 2013; Afiunizadeh & Karimzadeh, 2015).

Genus: *Muscidifurax* Girault & Sanders, 1910

76. *Muscidifurax raptor* Girault & Sanders, 1910*

Host: House fly pupae (Iranpour, Tirgari & Shayeghi, 1991).

Distribution in Iran: Alborz, Chaharmahal-e Bakhtiari and Hormozgan provinces (Iranpour, Tirgari & Shayeghi, 1991).

Genus: *Nasonia* Ashmead, 1904

77. *Nasonia vitripennis* (Walker, 1836)*

Host: It is a polyembryonic parasitoid of house fly Pupae (Iranpour, Tirgari & Shayeghi, 1991).

Distribution in Iran: Alborz, Chaharmahal-e Bakhtiari and Hormozgan provinces (Iranpour, Tirgari & Shayeghi, 1991).

Genus: *Norbanus* Walker 1843

78. *Norbanus arcuatus* Xiao & Huang, 2001*

Host: *Astragalus meridionalis* Bunge (Fabaceae) (Hesami et al., 2010).

Distribution in Iran: Fars province (Hesami et al., 2010).

79. *Norbanus calabrus* (Masi, 1942)

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan province (Lotfalizadeh, 2015).

80. *Norbanus cerasiops* (Masi, 1922)

Host: Collected by Malaise trap in Iran. Probably primary parasitoid of beetles of the genera *Lixus* Fabricius, 1801 and *Larinus* Dejean, 1821 (Curculionidae) in stems of *Cirsium* (Mill.), *Carduus* (L.), *Onopordon* (Vill.), *Amaranthus* (L.) or *Crambe* (L.) (Dzhanokmen, 1999; Rizzo & Mitroiu, 2010).

Distribution in Iran: Khorasan Razavi province (Hasani, Mitroiu & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

81. *Norbanus meridionalis* (Masi, 1922)*

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: West-Azarbaijan province (Lotfalizadeh, 2015).

82. *Norbanus obscurus* (Masi, 1922)**Host:** Unknown.**Distribution in Iran:** East-Azarbaijan, West-Azarbaijan and Kordestan provinces (Lotfalizadeh, 2015).**83. *Norbanus rasplusi* Lotfalizadeh, 2015*****Host:** Probably parasitoid of some seed-eater insects (Coleoptera and Lepidoptera) that attack *Dorema ammoniacum* (D. Don.).**Distribution in Iran:** Recently described based on collection from Iran: Fars and West-Azarbaijan provinces (Lotfalizadeh, 2015).**84. *Norbanus scabriculus* (Nees, 1834)****Host:** Unknown.**Distribution in Iran:** Qazvin province (Lotfalizadeh, 2015).**Genus:** *Pachyneuron* Walker, 1833**85. *Pachyneuron aphidis* (Bouché, 1834)****Host:** This species was reared from *Aphis gossypii* Glover, 1877 on cotton and *Brevicoryne brassicae* (L.) on Rape seed (*Brassica napus* L.).**Distribution in Iran:** Ardabil (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008), Tehran (Haeselbarth, 1983; Rakhshani *et al.*, 2004), Kerman (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011) and Khorasan Razavi provinces (Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).**86. *Pachyneuron erzurumicum* Doğanlar, 1986****Host:** Unknown.**Distribution in Iran:** Ilam (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008), Kerman (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011) and Khorasan Razavi provinces (Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).**87. *Pachyneuron formosum* Walker, 1833****Host:** Unknown.**Distribution in Iran:** Ilam province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).**88. *Pachyneuron grande* Thomson, 1878****Host:** *Pterocomma populeum* (Kaltenbach, 1843.) (Sadeghi & Ebrahimi, 2001).**Distribution in Iran:** Northern costal region of Iran (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).**89. *Pachyneuron groenlandicum* Holmgren, 1872****Host:** This species was reared on *Phleomyzus passerini* Signoret in Iran (Karadj city) by M. Abai (Haeselbarth, 1983).**Distribution in Iran:** Alborz (Haeselbarth, 1983), Ilam (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008), Khorasan Razavi (Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012) and Kerman provinces (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011).**90. *Pachyneuron leucopiscida* Mani, 1939****Host:** This species is hyperparasitoid of *Aphis gossypii* Glover, 1877 and *Aphis craccivora* Koch, 1854 parasitized by *Lysiphlebus fabarum* (Marshall, 1896) (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).**Distribution in Iran:** Fars, Alborz (Ebrahimi, 2014), Tehran (Haeselbarth, 1989) and Kordestan provinces (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2013, 2016).**91. *Pachyneuron muscarum* Linnaeus, 1758****Host:** *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* Green, 1908 is considered as host for this species (Ebrahimi, 2014). This species is considered as hyperparasitoid of *Eulecanium tiliae* (L. 1758), *Parthenolecanium corni* (Bouché, 1844) and other species of Hymenoptera and Diptera and also as primary parasitoid (Jalilvand *et al.*, 2013; Ebrahimi, 2014).**Distribution in Iran:** Fars, Alborz (Ebrahimi, 2014), Tehran (Haeselbarth, 1989) and Kermanshah provinces (Jalilvand *et al.*, 2013).**92. *Pachyneuron nelsoni* Girault, 1928*****Host:** This species is a gregarious parasitoid of hover flies (Dip.: Syrphidae) in pupal stage and was reared from syrphid fly (*Paragus* sp.) pupa by Lotfalizadeh and Gharali (2008).**Distribution in Iran:** East-Azarbaijan (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008) and Khorasan Razavi provinces (Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).

93. *Pachyneuron solitarium* Hartig, 1838*

Host: This species is hyperparasitoid of *Pemphigus spyrothecae* Passerini, 1860 via *Monoctonia vesicarii* Tremblay, 1991 (Hym.: Braconidae, Aphidiinae) (Ghafouri-Moghaddam, Lotfalizadeh & Rakhshani, 2014).
Distribution in Iran: Ardabil province (Ghafouri-Moghaddam, Lotfalizadeh & Rakhshani, 2014).

Genus: *Peridesmia* Förster, 1856**94. *Peridesmia discus* Walker, 1835***

Host: Unknown.
Distribution in Iran: East-Azərbayjan province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Pseudocatolaccus* Masi, 1908**95. *Pseudocatolaccus aragonensis* Askew, 2001**

Host: Unknown.
Distribution in Iran: Khorasan Razavi province (Hasani, Mitroiu & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

96. *Pseudocatolaccus nitescens* (Walker, 1834)*

Host: Unknown.
Distribution in Iran: East-Azərbayjan province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Psychophagus* Mayr, 1904**97. *Psychophagus omnivorus* (Walker, 1835)**

Host: *Hyphantria cunea* Drury, 1773 (Lep.: Arctiidae) (Rezaei, Moharrampour & Talebi, 2003).
Distribution in Iran: Caspian Sea coast (Rezaei, Moharrampour & Talebi, 2003).

Genus: *Pteromalus* Swederus, 1795**98. *Pteromalus albipennis* Walker, 1835***

Host: This species is reared from fruit flies (Dip.: Tephritidae) in safflower experimental field (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2014).
Distribution in Iran: East-Azərbayjan and Chaharmahal-e Bakhtiari provinces (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2014).

99. *Pteromalus bedeguaris* (Thomson, 1878)

Host: *Diplolepis mayri* Schlechtendal, 1876 and *Diplolepis fructuum* Rübsaamen, 1882

(Hym.: Cynipidae) (Lotfalizadeh, Rajabi & Madjdzadeh, 2012b).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azərbayjan (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008) and Kerman provinces (Lotfalizadeh, Rajabi & Madjdzadeh, 2012b).

100. *Pteromalus bifoveolatus* Förster, 1861

Host: Gregarious parasitoid of *Vespa orientalis* L., 1771 (Hym.: Vespidae) (Heidari et al., 2004). Larval parasitoid of *Malocosoma castrense* L., 1758 (Lep.: Lasiocampidae) (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: Alborz province (Heidari et al. 2004).

101. *Pteromalus chlorospilus* (Walker, 1834)*

Host: This species is considered as parasitoid of *Oxystoma ochropus* Germar, 1818 (Col.: Brentidae) which is associated with grass pea (*Lathyrus sativa* L.) (Hashemi & Lotfalizadeh, 2014).

Distribution in Iran: Ardabil province (Hashemi & Lotfalizadeh, 2014).

102. *Pteromalus puparum* Linnaeus, 1758

Host: *Pieris brassicae* L. (Lep.: Pieridae) and *Papilio demoleus* L., 1758 (Lep.: Papilionidae) (Farid, 1987; Razmi, Karimpour & Safaralizadeh, 2011).

Distribution in Iran: Tehran (Davatchi & Chodjai, 1968), Urmia (Razmi, Karimpour & Safaralizadeh, 2011) Sistan- Baluchestan (Farid, 1987) and Khorasan Razavi provinces (Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).

103. *Pteromalus sequester* Walker, 1835*

Host: Larval-pupal parasitoid of *Hyphenidium oculatum* Becker, 1913 (Dip.: Tephritidae) (Mohammadi-Khoramabadi et al. 2014).

Distribution in Iran: Yazd province (Mohammadi-Khoramabadi et al. 2014).

104. *Pteromalus veneris* Dalla Torre, 1898*

Host: *Megachila rotundata* Fabricius, 1787 (Mirabzadeh, 1989).

Distribution in Iran: Iran (no locality cited) (Mirabzadeh, 1989 as *P. venustus* Walker, 1835).

Genus: *Rhaphitelus* Walker, 1834**105. *Rhaphitelus maculatus* Walker, 1834***

Host: This species is reported as a parasitoid of xylophagous beetles and especially as an important agent in control of *Ruguloscolytus mediterraneus* Eggers, 1922 (Col.: Scolytidae) and *X. relexicauda* (Col.: Bostrychidae) in Iran (Lotfalizadeh & Khalghani, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: Markazi, Zanjan, Hamedan, Esfahan (Radjabi, 1991), East-Azarbaijan (Lotfalizadeh & Khalghani, 2008), Alborz and Ardabil provinces (Davatchi & Chodjai, 1968).

Genus: *Schizonotus* Ratzeburg, 1852**106. *Schizonotus sieboldi* Ratzeburg, 1848**

Host: *Melasoma populi* Linnaeus, 1758 (Col.: Chrysomelidae) (Lotfalizadeh & Ahmadi, 1998).

Distribution in Iran: Fars, Ilam (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008), Alborz provinces (Sadeghi & Askary, 2001).

Genus: *Spaniopus* Walker, 1833**107. *Spaniopus dissimilis* Walker, 1833***

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Ilam province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

108. *Spaniopus polypilus* Graham, 1956*

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Ilam province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Sphegigaster* Spinola, 1811**109. *Sphegigaster cuscatae* Ferrière, 1959**

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Khorasan Razavi province (Hasani, Mitroiu & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

110. *Sphegigaster ineus* Mitroiu, 2008*

Host: *Phyllonorycter medicaginella* Gerasimor, 1930 (Lep.: Gracillariidae) (Lotfalizadeh, 2015).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan province (Lotfalizadeh, Pourhaji & Zargaran, 2015).

111. *Sphegigaster mutica* Thomson, 1878*

Host: Unknown. This species was swept on *Trifolium* sp. in Kordestan province (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2016).

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2016).

112. *Sphegigaster nigricornis* Nees, 1834*

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: East-Azarbaijan and Ilam provinces (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

113. *Sphegigaster orobanchiae* Kurdjumov, 1912

Host: Agromyzidae (Dip.) (OILB, 1971).

Distribution in Iran: Unknown.

114. *Sphegigaster persiana* Mitroiu & Madjdzadeh, 2011

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Kerman province (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

115. *Sphegigaster truncata* Thomson, 1878

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Kerman province (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011).

Genus: *Stenetra* Masi, 1931**116. *Stenetra* sp.***

Host: Reared from seeds of *Sphora alopecuroides* Linnaeus, 1753 (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: Qazvin province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Stenomalina* Ghesquière, 1946**117. *Stenomalina* cf. *iera* (Walker, 1844)***

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Khorasan Razavi province (Hasani & Madjdzadeh, 2012).

Genus *Stenoselma* Delucchi, 1956**118. *Stenoselma nigrum* Delucchi, 1956**

Host: Reared from Buprestidae and Curocolionidae (Coleoptera), Cynipidae (Hymenoptera), Sesiidae (Lepidoptera) (Noyes, 2016).

Distribution in Iran: Kordestan province (Nazemi Rafie, Alipanah & Lotfalizadeh, 2011; Dehdar & Madjdzadeh, 2013).

Genus: *Syntomopus* Walker, 1833

119. *Syntomopus incisus* Thomson, 1878*

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: Ilam province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Thureonella* Gijswijt, 1990

120. *Thureonella* sp.*

Host: Unknown

Distribution in Iran: Ilam province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Trichomalus* Thomson, 1878

121. *Trichomalus campestris* Walker, 1834*

Host: Apionidae (Col.) (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azərbayjan province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

122. *Trichomalus rufinus* Walker, 1835*

Host: Unknown.

Distribution in Iran: East-Azərbayjan province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Genus: *Trychnosoma* Graham, 1957**

123. *Trychnosoma punctipleura* (Thomson, 1878)**

Material examined: IRAN, Qazvin province, Qazvin, summer 2010, Pan trap, (H. Lotfalizadeh), 1♀.

Comments: *Trychnosoma punctipleura* is parasitoid of Curculionidae (Col.) in Europe (Noyes, 2016). This is new record of genus and species from Iran.

Distribution in Iran: Qazvin province (new record for Iran).

Genus: *Urolepis* Walker, 1846

124. *Urolepis maritima* Walker, 1834

Host: *Ephydra afganica* (Dahl, 1981) (Dip.: Ephydridae), Agromyzidae, Anthomyiidae, Coelopidae, Ephydridae, Muscidae, Piophilidae, Sarcophagidae, Sepsidae and Syrphidae (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran, Fars (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008), Tehran and Esfahan provinces (Gibson, 2000).

Subfamily 9. Spalangiinae

Genus: *Spalangia* Latreille, 1805

125. *Spalangia endius* Walker, 1839*

Host: *Musca domestica* Linnaeus, 1758 (Behbahani, Tirgary & Ghasemi, 1995).

Distribution in Iran: Iran (no locality cited) (Behbahani, Tirgary & Ghasemi, 1995).

126. *Spalangia nigroaenea* Curtis, 1839*

Host: Muscidae, Calliphoridae and Sarcophagidae (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azərbayjan province (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008).

127. *Spalangia rugulosa* Förster, 1850**

Material examined: IRAN, East-Azərbayjan province, Marand, 28-VII-2007, Malaise trap, (H. Lotfalizadeh), 1♀ and 1♂.

Comments: This species has been reported as parasitoid of Muscidae (Diptera) from Europe (Noyes, 2016). Three species of the subfamily Spalangiinae has been reported from Iran (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008) but *S. rugulosa* is new record for Iran.

Distribution in Iran: East-Azərbayjan province (new record for Iran).

128. *Spalangia subpunctata* Förster, 1850*

Host: Syrphidae (*Syrietta pipiens* Linnaeus, 1758) and Otitidae (*Physiphora demandata* Fabricius, 1798) (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008). House fly pupae (Iranpour, Tirgary & shayeghi, 1991).

Distribution in Iran: East-Azərbayjan (Lotfalizadeh & Gharali, 2008), Alborz, Chaharmahal-e Bakhtiari and Hormozgan provinces (Iranpour, Tirgary & shayeghi, 1991).

Subfamily 10. Sycoryctinae

Genus: *Philotrypesis* Förster, 1878

129. *Philotrypesis caricae* (Linnaeus, 1762)*

Host: This species is cleptoparasitoid of the fig wasp, *Blastophaga psenes* Linnaeus, 1758 (Lotfalizadeh, Hosseini & Rasplus, 2014).

Distribution in Iran: Fars province (Lotfalizadeh, Hosseini & Rasplus, 2014).

Discussion

The provided checklist presents 129 species to Iran. One genus, *Trychnosoma* and four species, *Chalcedectus sinaiticus*, *Systasis ephedrae*, *Trychnosoma punctipleura* and *Spalangia rugulosa* are recorded for the first time for pteromalid fauna of Iran. Number of the genera and species of the above mentioned subfamilies in Iran are compared with these numbers in the world represented in Table 1. Iranian fauna of Pteromalidae belongs to 11.5% and 3.6% of the world known genera and species, respectively. The subfamily Pteromalinae is the most abundant subfamily while the subfamily Spalangiinae is the least abundant.

Iran constitutes a large part of the Iranian plateau. It covers an area of 1,623,779 km which is located between the

eastern Mediterranean area and the Oriental region, and contains elements of different fauna so the diverse topography and climate of Iran, from cool and humid mountains to hot and dry deserts, makes the country well suited ecologically for taxonomic studies (Zehzad, Kiabi & Madjnoonian, 2002). Local insects faunistic studies are of considerable importance in obtaining information that will help researchers to maintain, discover and protect the natural environment (Mitroiu, Abolhassanzadeh & Madjdzadeh, 2011). It is evident that the present survey should be considered as an important effort in this direction and add new records which expand our knowledge on faunal diversity of Iran. Apparently the pteromalid fauna of Iran is richer and needs more investigations and samplings in different regions of the country.

Table 1. Number of genera and species of the subfamilies of Pteromalidae in Iran in comparison to the world.

Subfamily	Number of Genera		Number of Species	
	World	Iran	World	Iran
Asaphinae	6	1	29	2
Cerocephalinae	14	1	43	2
Cleonyminae	42	6	284	7
Colotrechninae	20	1	42	1
Eunotinae	23	3	91	3
Miscogasterinae	36	3	340	11
Ormocerinae	42	1	179	7
Pteromalinae	317	44	2319	91
Spalangiinae	2	1	67	4
Sycoryctinae	11	1	151	1
Total	513	62	3545	129

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

- Afiunizadeh, M., Karimzadeh, J. & Lotfalizadeh, H. (2013) *Mokrzeckia obscura* (Hym.: Pteromalidae), a hyperparasitoid of diamondback moth and a new record from Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 33(2), 91.
- Afiunizadeh, M. & Karimzadeh, J. (2015) Assessment of naturally occurring parasitism of diamondback moth in field

- using recruitment method. *Archives of Phytopathology and Plant Protection*, 48(1), 43–49. Available from : <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/03235408.2014.882113>.
- Alemansour, H., Asadi, R. & Alehosein, S.A. (2010) Introduction of hymenopteran parasitoid of *Eurytoma* sp. (Hym.: Eurytomidae), a seed pest of medicinal plant *Ephedra procera* (Ephedraceae) in Fars Province, Iran. Proceedings of the 19th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 31 July- 3 August 2010, Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection, Tehran, Vol. 1. Pests, p. 163.
- Alipanah, V., Nazemi-Rafie, J. & Lotfalizadeh, H. (2013) First report of three species of pteromalid wasps (Hym.: Pteromalidae) from Iran. *Journal of Plant Protection*, 26(4), 492–493.
- Askew, R.R. (1972) A revision of the British species of *Halticoptera* (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae) allied to *H. circulus* (Walker). *Journal of Entomology* (B), 41(1), 45–52.
- Askew, R.R. (1961) A study of the biology of species of the genus *Mesopolobus* Westwood (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae) associated with cynipid galls on oak. *Transactions of the Royal Entomological Society of London*, 113(8), 155–173. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2311.1961.tb00806.x>.
- Askew, R.R., Sadeghi, S.E. & Tavakoli, M. (2006) Chalcidoidea (Hym.) in galls of *Diplolepis mayri* (Schlechtendal) (Hym.: Cynipidae) in Iran, with the description of a new species of *Pseudotorymus* Masi (Hym.: Torymidae). *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine*, 142, 1–6.
- Assemi, H. & Shojai, M. (2004) Introduction of a pupal parasitoid species of *Sitophilus oryzae* L. (Col.: Curculionidae) for Mazandaran province fauna, Iran. Proceeding of the 16th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 28 Aug.-1 Sep. University of Tabriz, p. 141.
- Bahri-Motlagh, S., Lotfalizadeh, H. & Mehrvar, A. (2012) New record of *Anognmus laricis* (Bouček) (Hym.: Pteromalidae) from Iran. *Applied Entomology and Phytopathology*, 80(1), 101–102.
- Bayegan, Z., Lotfalizadeh, H., Zargarán, M.R. & Pooraiouby, R. (2014) New record of the genus and species *Callitula ferrierei* (Bouček) (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae) from Iran. *Journal of Crop Protection*, 3(2), 125–128.
- Bayegan, Z., Lotfalizadeh, H. & Zargarán, M.R. (2015) Occurrence of eulophid wasps (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea, Eulophidae) in rice fields of eastern Guilan, Iran. *Journal of Crop Protection*, 4(2), 199–205.
- Behbahani, A., Tiryary, S. & Ghasemi, M.J. (1995) New record of *Spalangia endius* Walker (Hym.: Pteromalidae), pupal parasitoid of house fly and its biology and mass rearing in Iran. Proceeding of the 12th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 2-7 September 1995, Teharan University, Karaj, Iran, p. 291.
- Bouček, Z. (1958) To the taxonomy of the European species of *Schizonotus* and *Caenocrepis* parasites of economic importance - with notes, and some synonymy in Pteromalidae and Eurytomidae (Hym.). *Sborník Entomologického Oddelení Národního Musea v Praze*, 32, 395–404.
- Bouček, Z. (1963) A taxonomic study in *Spalangia* Lat. (Hym.: Chalcidoidea). *Sborník Entomologického Oddelení Národního Musea v Praze*, 35, 429–512.
- Bouček, Z. (1972) On European Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera): A revision of *Cleonymus*, *Eunotus* and *Spaniopus*, with descriptions of new genera and species. *Bulletin of the British Museum (Natural History) Entomology*, 27(9), 265–315.
- Bouček, Z. (1988) Australasian Chalcidoidea (Hymenoptera). *A biosystematic revision of genera of fourteen families, with a reclassification of species*. CAB International, Wallingford, Oxon, U.K., Cambrian News Ltd, Aberystwyth, Wales, 832 pp.
- Bouček, Z. & Rasplus, J.-Y. (1991) *Illustrated key to West-Palaearctic genera of Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera - Chalcidoidea)*. INRA Editions, série Techniques et Pratiques, Paris, 140 pp.
- Campbell, B., Heraty, J., Rasplus J.-Y., Chan, K., Steffen-Campbell, J. & Babcock, C. (2000) Molecular systematics of the Chalcidoidea using 28S-D2 rDNA. In: Austin A.D., Dowton, M. (Eds), *Hymenoptera evolution, biodiversity and biological control*. CSIRO Publishing, Collingwood, Australia, pp. 59–73.

- Damavandian M.R. & Feli Kohikheili, Z. (2015) New report of *Cleonymus laticornis* (Hym.: Pteromalidae) from Iran. *Applied Entomology and Phytopathology*, 83(1), 81-82.
- Davatchi, A. & Chodjai, M. (1968) *Les Hymenopteres entomophages de l'Iran..* Publication, Université de Teheran, Faculté d'Agronomie, Publication No 107, 1-88.
- Davoodi, A. (2004) Identification and host range of soft scale (Hom.: Coccidae) parasitoid wasps in Tehran and some other areas of Iran. MSc Dissertation, Tarbiat Modares University, Tehran, 143 pp.
- Davoodi, A., Talebi, A.A., Rajabi, G.R., Fathipour, Y., Rezaei, V. & Rakhshani, E. (2004) An Identification of parasitoids and Hyperparasitoids of the most common soft scales (Hom.: Coccidae) in Tehran and Guilan provinces. *Iranian Journal of Agricultural Science*, 35(4), 887-899.
- Debach, P. & Rosen, D. (1991) Biological control by natural enemies, second ed. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.
- Dehdar, K. & Madjdzadeh, S.M. (2013) A contribution to the knowledge of the pteromalid wasps (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Pteromalidae) of Kurdistan province, Western Iran including new records. *Biharean Biologist*, 7(2), 90-93.
- Dehdar K. & Madjdzadeh, S.M. (2016) Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) from Kordestan province, western Iran. *Far Eastern Entomologist*, 315, 11-20.
- Desjardins, C.A., Regier, J.C. & Mitter, C. (2007) Phylogeny of pteromalid parasitic wasps (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae): Initial evidence from four protein-coding nuclear genes. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 45, 454-469.
- Doğanlar M. (1986) Morphological studies of the hypopygium and its importance to the taxonomy of the genera *Pachyneuron* and *Euneura* (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae), with description of a new species of *Pachyneuron* from Turkey. *Fen-Edebyiat Fakültesi Fen Bil. Derg.* 4, 23-32.
- Doğanlar, M. & Bolu, H. (2004) A new species of *Gugolzia* Delucchi and Steffan (Hym., Pteromalidae) from Turkey, a parasitoid of *Eurytoma amygdali* Enderlein (Hym., Eurytomidae). *Zoology in the Middle East*, 32, 75-78.
- Dzhanokmen, K.A. (1978) *Hymenoptera III. Chalcidoidea 5. Pteromalidae.* Opredelitel' Nasekomikh Evropeyskoy Chasti SSSR: 57-228 pp.
- Dzhanokmen, K.A. (1989) Trophic links of the pteromalid wasps with the Diptera. *Entomological Review*, 68(3), 92-98.
- Dzhanokmen, K.A. (1990) Trophic association of parasitic Hymenoptera of the family Pteromalidae. *Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie*, 119(4), 764-781.
- Dzhanokmen, K.A. (1996) A review of pteromalids of the genus *Systasis* (Hymenoptera, Chalcidoidea, Pteromalidae) from Kazakhstan. *Entomological Review*, 76(7), 935-947.
- Dzhanokmen, K.A. (2001) A review of pteromalids of the genus *Pteromalus* Swederus (Hymenoptera, Pteromalidae) of Kazakhstan. II. *Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie*, 80(2), 472-496.
- Ebrahimi, E. (2014) Parasitoid and hyperparasitoid wasps of scale insects in Hayk Mirzayans Insect Museum, Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 34(1), 73-83.
- Emami, S.Y. & Mehrnejad, M.R. (2004) The situation of weed aphids parasitoid and hyperparasitoids in pistachio orchards of Kerman province. Proceeding of the 16th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 28 Aug.-1 Sep., Univ. of Tabriz, Iran, p. 19.
- Eslami, J. (1998) The proof of larval gregarism in *Dinarmus vagabundus* (Hym.: Pteromalidae) and a study of some of its population problems. Proceeding of the 13th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 23-27 August, Teheran University, Karaj, Iran, p. 70.
- Farid, A. (1987) Some bio-ecological features of citrus butterflies in south-east Iran. *Entomologie et Phytopathologie Appliquées*, 54 (1-2), 129-137.
- Farooqi, S.I. & Menon, M.G.R. (1972) A new phytophagous species of *Systasis* Walker (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae) infesting seeds of *Cenchrus* species. *Mushi*, 46(9), 111-114.

- Ghafouri-Moghaddam, M., Lotfalizadeh, H. & Rakhshani, E. (2014) A survey on hyperparasitoids of the poplar spiral gall aphid, *Pemphigus spyrothecae* Passerini (Hemiptera: Aphididae) in Northwest Iran. *Journal of Crop Protection*, 3(3), 369–376.
- Gharizadeh, E. & Hesami, Sh. (2003) Report of *Metastenus concinnus* (Hym.: Pteromalidae) parasitoid of *Cryptolaemus montrouzieri* in Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 22(2), 86.
- Gibson, G.A.P., Heraty, J.M. & Woolly, J.B. (1999) Phylogenetics and classification of Chalcidoidea and Mymarommatoidea—a review of current concepts (Hymenoptera, Apocrita). *Zoologica Scripta*, 28: 87–124. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1046/j.1463-6409.1999.00016.x>.
- Gibson, G.A.P. (2000) Differentiation of the species of *Urolepis* (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Pteromalidae), potential biocontrol agents of filth flies (Diptera: Muscidae). *Canadian Entomologist*, 132 (4), 391–410. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent132391-4>.
- Gibson, G.A.P. (2001) The Australian species of *Pachyneuron* Walker (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Pteromalidae). *Journal of Hymenoptera Research*, 10(1), 29–54.
- Goldansaz, H., Esmaili, M. & Ebadi, R. (1996) Lesser wax moth, *Achroia grisella* Fab. and its parasitic wasps. Proceedings of the XX International Congress of Entomology, Firenze, Italy, 25–31 August 1996, p. 663.
- Graham, M.W.R. de V. (1961) Three new species of the *Caenacis-Cecidostiba* group (Hym., Pteromalidae), and a British record of a fourth species. *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine*, 97, 171–176.
- Graham, M.W.R. de V. (1969) The Pteromalidae of north-western Europe (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea). *Bulletin of the British Museum (Natural History) (Entomology) Supplement*, 16, 908 pp.
- Graham, M.W.R. de V. (1972) Two new British species of *Halticoptera* (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea, Pteromalidae). *Journal of Entomology (B)*, 41(2), 103–106.
- Graham, M.W.R. de V. (1992) The European species of the genus *Conomorium* Masi, 1924 (Hym., Pteromalidae) including one new to science. *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine*, 128, 197–202.
- Greathead, D.J. (1986) Parasitoids in classical biological control. pp. 287–318. In: Waag, J.K., Greathead, D.J. (Eds), *Insect parasitoids*. Academic Press, London.
- Habibpour, B., Kamali, K. & Meidani, J. (2002) Insects and mites associated with stored products and their arthropod parasites and predators in Khuzestan province (Iran). *Bulletin Section Regionale Ouest Palaearctique, Organisation Internationale de Lutte Biologique*, 25(3), 89–91.
- Hadi, O., Kazemi, M.-H. & Lotfalizadeh, H. (2017) New record of the genus and species of *Ksenoplata quadrata* Bouček (Hym.: Pteromalidae) on *Ephedra major* in Iran. *Applied Entomology and Phytopathology*, 84(2), 359–361.
- Haeselbarth, E. (1983) Determination list of entomophagous insects. No. 11. *Bulletin Section Regionale Ouest Palaearctique, Organisation Internationale de Lutte Biologique*, 12(7), 1–62.
- Hasani, A., Mitroiu, M.-D. & Madjdzadeh, S.M. (2011) New records of Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) from Northeastern Iran. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica*, 63(3), 323–325.
- Hasani, A. & Madjdzadeh, S.M. (2012) Contribution to the knowledge of the Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) from Khorasan Razavi province, Northeastern Iran. *Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics*, 8 (1), 57–69.
- Hashemi, S. M. & Lotfalizadeh, H. (2014) Hymenopterous parasitoids of *Oxystoma ochropus* (Germar) (Col.: Brentidae) in Ardabil province. Proceedings of the 21th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 23–26 August, Urmia University, Iran, p. 728.
- Hedquist, K.J. (1975) Notes on Chalcidoidea VII—A key to Swedish species of the genus *Halticoptera* Spin and three related genera (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae). *Entomologica Scandinavica*, 6, 167–181.
- Heidari, S., Fathipour, Y., Sadeghi, S.E. & Baur, H. (2004) Report of *Pteromalus bifoveolatus* (Hym.: Pteromalidae) from Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 24(1), 133–134.

- Herting, B. (1973) *Coleoptera to Strepsiptera. A catalogue of parasites and predators of terrestrial arthropods. Section A. Host or Prey/Enemy.* Commonwealth Agricultural Bureaux, Institute of Biological Control 3: 114 pp.
- Hesami, SH., Seyedebrahimi, S., Gheibi, M. & Zareie, R. (2010). Occurrence of four species of Hymenoptera associated with *Astragalus meridionalis* in Fars province of Iran. Proceedings of 19th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 31 July- 3 August 2010, Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection, Tehran, Vol. 1. Pests, p. 124.
- Huber J.T. & Vayssieres, J.F. (1990) Life cycle and host specificity of the heliotrope weevil *Pachycerus cordiger* equals *madidius* auct. (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *Entomophaga*, 35(3), 475-484.
- Iranpour M., Targari S., & Shayeghi, M. (1991) First attempt on the study of the biology and mass rearing of two Iranian parasitoids of hous fly pupae. Proceeding of the 10th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 1-2 September 1991, Shahid Bahonar University of Kerman, Iran, p. 14.
- Jafari, A. & Shaigan, A. (1993) Introduction of some parasitoids of *Kermania pistaciella* Amsel. Proceeding of the 11h Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 28 Aug. - 1 Sept., Rasht, Iran, p. 191.
- Jalilvand, N. & Gholipour, Y. (2002) Pistachio production in Iran: II. Main Iranian pistachio pests. *NUCIS Newsletter*, 11, 23-25.
- Jalilvand, K., Shirazi, M., Vahedi, H. A., Fallahzadeh, M., Naghadeh, N. M. & Samih, M. A. (2013) A Preliminary Study on Natural Enemies of Coccoidea (Hemiptera, Sternorrhyncha) in Kermanshah Province, Western Iran. *Acta Phytopathologica et Entomologica Hungarica*, 48(2), 299-308. Available from : <http://dx.doi.org/10.1556/APhyt.48.2013.2.11>.
- Kazemi, F., Talebi, A.A., Fathipour Y., & Moharrampour, S. (2004) Host stage preference and functional response of *Anisopteromalus calandrae* (Hym.: Pteromalidae), a larval parasitoid of *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Col.: Bruchidae) on chickpea in laboratory conditions. Proceeding of the 16th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 28 August-1 September 2004, University of Tabriz, Iran, p. 29.
- Kazemi, F., Talebi, A.A. & Fathipour Y. (2010) The reproduction and population growth parameters of *Anisopteromalus calandrae* (Hym.: Pteromalidae), a parasitoid of *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Col.: Bruchidae). *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 29(2), 1-10.
- Lotfalizadeh, H. & Ahmadi, A.A. (1998) New record of *Schizonotus sieboldi* Ratzeburg (Hym.: Pteromalidae), pupal parasitoid of poplar leaf beetle, *Chrysomela populi* L. (Col.: Chrysomelidae) from Iran. *Applied Entomology and Phytopathology*, 66(1/2), 45-46.
- Lotfalizadeh, H. & Ahmadi, A.A. (2000) Natural enemies of cypress tree mealybug, *Planococcus vovae* (Nasonov), and their parasitoids in Shiraz, Iran. *Iran Agricultural Research*, 19(2), 145-154.
- Lotfalizadeh, H. (2002a) Parasitoids of cabbage aphid, *Brevicoryne brassicae* (L.) (Hom.: Aphididae) in Moghan region. *Agricultural Science*, 12(1), 15-25.
- Lotfalizadeh, H. (2002b) Natural enemies of cotton aphids in Moghan region. Proceeding of the 15th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 7-11 September 2002, Razi University, Kermanshah, p. 36, 37.
- Lotfalizadeh H. (2004) Introduction of two species of the genus *Spalangia* Lat. (Hym.: Pteromalidae) from Iran. Proceeding of the 16th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 28 August-1 September 2004, University of Tabriz, Iran, p. 114.
- Lotfalizadeh, H., Rasplus, J.-Y. & Delvare, G. (2006) Rose gall wasps and their associated fauna (Hymenoptera) in Iran. *Redia*, LXXXIX: 73-85.
- Lotfalizadeh, H. & Gharali, B. (2008) Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) of Iran: New records and a preliminary checklist. *Entomofauna*, 29 (6), 93-120.
- Lotfalizadeh, H. & Khalghani, J. (2008) Hymenopterous parasitoids (Hym.: Chalcidoidea) of xylophagous beetles in Iran. *Entomofauna*, 29 (19), 249-264.
- Lotfalizadeh, H. & Gharali, B. (2014) Hymenopterous parasitoids of safflower

- seed pests in Iran. *Applied Entomology and Phytopathology*, 82(1), 1-11.
- Lotfalizadeh, H. & Hosseini, F. (2014) Chalcidoid parasitoids (Hymenoptera) of *Etiella zinckenella* (Treitschke) (Lep.: Pyralidae) on *Sophora alopecuroides* L. in Iran. *North-Western Journal of Zoology*, 10(2), 251-258.
- Lotfalizadeh, H., Hosseini, F. & Rasplus, J.-Y. (2014) The subfamily Sycoryctinae (Hym.: Pteromalidae): New record for Iranian fauna. Proceedings of the 21th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 23-26 August 2014, Urmia University, p. 678.
- Lotfalizadeh, H., Masnadi-Yazdinejad, A. & Saber, M. (2012a) New records of the Grape berry moth hymenopterous parasitoids in Iran. *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 7(1), 284-291.
- Lotfalizadeh, H., Rajabi, M. & Madjdzadeh, S. M. (2012b) Parasitoids community of *Diplolepis fructuum* (Rübsaamen) (Hym.: Cynipidae) in Kerman Province, with checklist of its associated Hymenoptera fauna in Iran. *North- Western journal of Zoology*, 8(1), 125-131.
- Lotfalizadeh, H., Pourhaji, A. & Zargarani, M.R. (2015) Hymenopterous parasitoids (Hymenoptera: Braconidae, Eulophidae, Pteromalidae) of the alfalfa leafminers in Iran and their diversity. *Far Eastern Entomology*, 288, 1-24.
- Lotfalizadeh, H., Bayegan, Z. A. & Zargarani, M. R. (2016) Species diversity of Chalcidoidea (Hymenoptera) in the rice fields of Iran. *Journal of Entomological Research Society*, 18(1), 99-111.
- Lotfalizadeh, H. (2015) Review of the Iranian Pteromalinae with spiculated antennae, and description of a new species of *Norbanus* Walker (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea, Pteromalidae). *Zootaxa*, 4013(3), 428-434. Available from : <http://dx.doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4013.3.6>.
- Lotfalizadeh, H., Alehosein, S.A., & Fallahzadeh, M. (2017) Two new records of the subfamily Cleonyminae (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae) from Iran. *Journal of Insect Biodiversity and Systematics*, 3(1), 41-45.
- Mahdavi, M. & Madjdzadeh, S.M. (2013) Contribution to the knowledge of Chalcidoidea (Pteromalidae and Eupelmidae) of Iran. *North- Western journal of Zoology*, 9 (1), 94-98.
- Mahdavi, M., Madjdzadeh, S.M. & Mitroiu, M-D. (2015) Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) associated with plant galls in the south-eastern Iran, with three new records. *Journal of Insect Biodiversity and Systematics*, 1(1), 47-54.
- Mashhadi-Jafarloo, M. & Talebi-Chaichi, P. (2002) Bioecology of *Dibrachys boarmiae* (Walker) (Hym.: Pteromalidae) in East Azarbaijan. Proceeding of the 15th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 7-11 September 2002, Kermanshah, Iran, p. 86, 87.
- Mehrnejad, M.R. (2002) The natural parasitism ratio of the pistachio twig borer moth, *Kermania pistaciella*, In Iran. *Acta Horticulturae*, 591: Available from : <http://dx.doi.org/541-544.10.17660/ActaHortic.2002.591.83>.
- Mehrnejad, M.R. (2003) The influence of host species of some biological and behavioural aspects of *Dibrachys boarmiae* (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae), parasitoid of *Kermania pistaciella* (Lepidoptera: Tineidae). *Biocontrol Science and Technology*, 13(2), 219-229.
- Mirabzadeh, A. (1989) Natural enemies of megachil. Proceeding of the 9th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 9-14 September 1989, Ferdowsi University, Mashhad, Iran, p. 56.
- Mirkarimi, A. (1998) Description of egg and larval stages of *Asaphes suspensus* (Nees) (Hym.: Pteromalidae), hyperparasitoid of potato aphid in laboratory. Proceedings of the 13th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 23-27 August, Karaj, Iran, p. 98.
- Mitroiu, M.D, Abolhassanzadeh, F. & Madjdzadeh, S.M. (2011) New records of Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) from Iran, with description of a new species. *North Western Journal of Zoology*, 7(2), 243-249.
- Mitroiu, M.D. (2012) The genus *Caenocrepis* Thomson (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae) in the Afrotropical region, with a key to world species. *Zootaxa*, 3557, 49-55.
- Mitroiu, M.D. (2014) An atypical new species of *Halticoptera* Spinola (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae) from Valea lui David natural

- reserve, Romania. *North Western Journal of Zoology*, 10 (suppl. 1), 22–26.
- Mohammadi-Khoramabadi, A., Lotfalizadeh, H., Gharali, B. & Moghadam, M. (2014) Two new records of Chalcidoidea (Hymenoptera) from Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 34(2), 1–2.
- Nazemi-Rafie, J. & Lotfalizadeh, H. (2010) *Oodera monstrem* Nikol's kaya, 1952 (Hym.: Pteromalidae): a new generic and specific record for Iran. Proceeding of 19 th Iranian plant protection congress, Tehran, Iran. P.145. (in Persian, with English summary).
- Nazemi-Rafie, J., Alipanah, V. & Lotfalizadeh, H. (2011) Report of five species of Pteromalidae (Hym.: Chalcidoidea) new for the Iranian fauna. *Plant Protection Journal*, 3(3), 211–222.
- Nikdel, M., Sadaghian, B., Dordaei, A.A., Askary, H. & Baur, H. (2007) Report of *Conomorium patulum* (Hym.: Pteromalidae) from Iran. *Iranian Journal of Forest and Range Protection Resaearch*, 4(2), 123–124.
- Noyes, J.S. (2016) Universal Chalcidoidea Database, World Wide Web electronic publication, Available from: <http://www.nhm.ac.uk/entomology/chalcids/index.html>. accessed at: 2016.12.20.
- OILB (1971) Liste d'identification des entomophages 8. OILB, Genève, 18 pp.
- Rajabi, Gh. (1991) *Insects attacking rosaceous fruit trees in Iran*. Vol. 1. Coleoptera. 2nd ed, Plant Pests & Disease Research Institue Publication, 221 pp. (in Persian).
- Rakhshani, E., Talebi, A.A., Sadeghi, E., Ebrahimi, E. & Rhurczy, S. (2003) Report of five wasp's species associated with dog rose galls in Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 23(1), 108.
- Rakhshani, E., Talebi, A.A., Sadeghi, E., Kavallieratos N. G. & Rashed, A. (2004) Sesonal parasitism and hyperparasitism of valnus aphidm *Chromaphis juglandicola* (Hom.: Aphididae) in Tehran province. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 23(2), 1–11.
- Razmi, M., Karimpour, Y. & Safaralizadeh, M. H. (2011) Parasitism of *Pieris Brassicae* (L.) (Lep.: Pieridae) on cabbage farms in comparison with wild hosts and study on use of *Pteromalus Puparum* (L.) (Hym. Pteromalidae), as a biological control agent versus this pest. *Munis Entomology and Zoology*, 6(1), 176–180.
- Rezaei, V., Moharramipour S. & Talebi, A.A. (2003) The first report of *Psychophagus omnivorus* (Walker) and *Chouioia cunea* (Yang) parasitoid wasps of American white webworm *Hyphantria cunea* Drury (Lep.: Arctiidae) from Iran. *Applied Entomology and Phytopathology*, 70(2), 33.
- Rizzo M.C. & Mitroiu, M.D. (2010) Revision of the European, North African and Central Asian species of the genus *Norbanus* Walker 1843 (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae). *Journal of Hymenoptera Research*, 19(2), 228–243.
- Russo G. (1959). Bio-ecological observations on *Dacus oleae* and control experiments in Ascea (Salerno) in 1958. *Bollettino del Laboratorio di Entomologia Agraria 'Filippo Silvestri', Portici*, 17, 260–360.
- Sadeghi, S.E. & Askary, H. (2001) Parasitism rate of *Schizonotus sieboldii* Ratzeburg (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae) a parasitoid of poplar leaf beetle pupa, on different poplar species. Proceedings of the International symposium on Parasitic Hymenoptera: taxonomy and biological control. 14–17 May, 2001, Kőszeg, Hungary. (Eds: Thuróczy, C.; Eke, I.; Káldy, J.; Melika, G.) Systematic parasitoid laboratory, Kőszeg, Hungary.
- Sadeghi, S.E. & Ebrahimi, E. (2002) New report of *Pachyneuron grande* Thomson (Hym.: Pteromalidae) from Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 21(1), 113–114.
- Sadeghi, S. & Lotfalizadeh, H. (2013) New record of *Halticoptera Polita* (Walker, 1834) (Hym.: Pteromalidae) from Iran. *Applied Entomology and Phytopathology*, 2(95), 187–188.
- Sharifi, S. & Javadi, I. (1971) Control of Rosaceae branch borer in Iran. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 64(2), 484–486.
- Steffan, J.R. (1968) Observations sur *Chalcedectus sinaiticus* (Ms.) et descriptions de *C. balachowskyi* sp.n. (Hym. Chalcedectidae) et d'*Oopristus safavii* gen.n., sp.n. (Hym.: Torymidae), deux parasites d'importance économique en Iran. *Entomophaga*, 13(3), 209–216.

- Stavraki, H. (1986) Two parasites of *Apion croceifemoratum* Gyllenhal (Curculionidae) reported for the first time in Greece. *Annales de l'Institut Phytopathologique Benaki*, 15(1), 91-92.
- Török, M. & Abraham, R. (2001) Sampling ground or truly monophyletic? Cladistic analyses applied to the phylogeny of Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea). In: Thuróczy C., Eke, I., Káldy, J. & Melika, G. (Eds.), International symposium: Parasitic Hymenoptera: taxonomy and biological control. 14-17 May, Systematic parasitoid laboratory, Köszeg, Hungary.
- Xiao, H. & Huang, D. (2001) A revision of *Systasis* Walker (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae) from China. *Zoological studies*, 40 (1), 7-13.
- Xiao, H., Polaszek, A. & Huang, D. (2005) A study of the genus *Callitula* Spinola (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae) from china. *Oreintal Insects*, 39, 233-240.
- Zehzad, B., Kiabi, B. H. & Madjnoonian, H. (2002) The natural areas and landscape of Iran: an overview. *Zoology in the Middle East*, 26, 7-10.
- Ziaaddini, M., Lotfalizadeh, H., Mohammadi Khoramabadi, A. & Jalali, M.A. (2014) First report of *Dibrachys lignicola* (Hym.: Pteromalidae) from Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 34(1), 97-98.

لیست به روز شده زنبورهای خانواده Pteromalidae (Hym.: Chalcidoidea) در ایران به همراه چند گزارش جدید

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چکیده: لیست به روز شده ۱۲۹ گونه از ۶۲ جنس متعلق به ۱۰ زیرخانواده از خانواده Pteromalidae (Hym.: Chalcidoidea) ایران ارایه شده است. جنس *Systasis ephedrae* Dzhankmen، و سه گونه *Trychnosoma* Graham, 1957، *Spalangia rugulosa* و *Trychnosoma punctipleura* Thomson, 1878، 1982 برای اولین بار برای فون ایران گزارش می‌شوند. میزبان‌ها و اطلاعات پراکنش این گونه‌ها در ایران ارایه شده‌اند.

واژگان کلیدی: کاتالوگ، پراکنش، میزبان‌ها، ایران، گزارش‌های جدید، Pteromalidae